

Extra-stabilisation of Mixed-ligand Complexes of *d*-Block Metal Ions with α, α' -Dipyridyl and Amino Acids

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Mixed-ligand complexes of the type [MAL], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, or Cd^{II}; A = α, α' -dipyridyl (dipy); L = α -alanine (α -ala), β -phenylalanine (β -phe) or tryptophan (trp), have been found to be extra-stabilised in aqueous medium. The extent of extra-stabilisation has been evaluated from a knowledge of the experimental values of formation constants of the MAL complexes. The formation constants have been determined by potentiometric pH-titrations using the Irving-Rossotti approach at 25° and at an ionic strength, $I = 0.2$ (mol dm⁻³; KNO₃). The [M.dipy.trp] complex is more extra-stabilised than the [M.dipy. β -phe] complex. Possible mechanism involved in extra-stabilisation has been discussed.

A mixed-ligand complex containing a ligand like α, α' -dipyridyl and an amino acid with a fairly large noncoordinating side chain may be considered^{1,2} as a relatively simple model for ternary systems like (enzyme metal ion. ATP) or (enzyme metal ion. inhibitor), which have biochemical importance. Such complexes may be 'extra-stabilised' in solution. The driving force of extra-stabilisation is believed to be hydrophobic in nature^{3,4}.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the possible extra-stabilisation of mixed-ligand complexes of the type [MAL], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; A = α, α' -dipyridyl (dipy); L = α -alanine (α -ala), β -phenylalanine (β -phe) or tryptophan (trp). The three amino acids may be considered as α -amino, α -amino- β -phenyl, and α -amino- β -indole derivatives, respectively, of propionic acid. Extra-stabilisation has been assessed from a knowledge of the formation constants of the mixed-ligand complexes.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of Loba/AnalaR grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The metal ion solutions were standardised by EDTA complexometric titrations⁵. The formation constants, $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ were determined by potentiometric pH-titrations using the Irving-Rossotti approach^{6,7} at 25° and at ionic strength, $I = 0.2$ (mol dm⁻³; KNO₃). The final metal and ligand concentrations (1:1:1) were maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³. The pH-titrations were performed using a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter having an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit, a microburette of 2 ml capacity reading upto 0.01 ml, and a carbonate-free 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution. The titrations were repeated to obtain

reproducible data. The proton-ligand formation constants were redetermined to obtain their $\log K_{\text{H}}^H$ values under the experimental conditions. The formation constants $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ were subjected to algebraic refinement by using the method of linear plots⁸, and to statistical refinement by applying the Q-test⁹. The calculated values of $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ and $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$ are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - FORMATION CONSTANTS, $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ AND $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$ VALUES*

	Temp. = 25°, $I = 0.2$ (mol dm ⁻³ ; KNO ₃)				
Formation constant	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
L = α -ala					
$\log K_{ML}^M$	4.71	5.83	7.83	5.29	4.85
	(± 0.03)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.02)
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.39	5.37	7.42	4.90	4.64
	(± 0.04)	(± 0.01)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.03)
$\Delta \log K$	-0.32	-0.46	-0.41	-0.39	-0.21
L = β -phe					
$\log K_{ML}^M$	3.89	4.83	7.34	4.57	4.21
	(± 0.03)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.01)
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.63	4.61	7.83	4.21	4.11
	(± 0.01)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.04)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.05)
$\Delta \log K$	-0.26	-0.22	0.49	-0.36	-0.10
L = trp					
$\log K_{ML}^M$	4.10	5.50	8.08	4.79	4.33
	(± 0.03)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.03)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.02)
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.63	5.89	8.83	5.16	4.72
	(± 0.02)	(± 0.01)	(± 0.04)	(± 0.01)	(± 0.02)
$\Delta \log K$	0.53	0.39	0.75	0.37	0.39

*Figures in parentheses represent standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

The nature of titration curves shows that the mixed-ligand complexes are formed in two steps : $M+A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA+L \rightleftharpoons MAL$. With Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} a slight tendency of the formation of hydroxo species $MA(OH)_n$ is indicated, but hydrolysis correction¹⁰ may be avoided without bringing in much approximation in the $\log K_{MAL}^M$ values. The experimental data (Table 1) show that the values of $\Delta \log K$ are uniformly negative with α -alanine. With β -phenylalanine, however, the values are less negative or even positive (with Cu^{II}), and with tryptophan they are all positive. These are important trends. One would normally expect the stability of MAL to decrease on going from α -ala to β -phe to trp in view of the gradual increase in the bulk of the noncoordinating side chain in L. A reverse trend indicates extra stabilisation of the mixed-ligand complexes with β -phe as well as trp. The extent of extra-stabilisation may be worked out by defining a stability quantifying factor $\Delta \Delta \log K$ as

$$\Delta \Delta \log K = \Delta \log K_1 - \Delta \log K_2 \quad (1)$$

where, $\Delta \log K_1$ and $\Delta \log K_2$ stand, respectively, for the experimental $\Delta \log K$ values for the 'large sized' (β -phe or trp) and 'small sized' (α -ala) secondary ligands. Small experimental errors in $\Delta \log K$ for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ternary systems may also get eliminated at least to a good extent in working out the $\Delta \Delta \log K$ values. One may, further, visualise the existence of an equilibrium in solution between the extra-stabilised, i.e. 'interacted' form of MAL (MAL_{int}) and its 'open' or 'uninteracted' form (MAL_{op}),

in view of the fact that such an extra-stabilisation

in some ternary systems^{11,12} has been found to vary with the size of the non-coordinating side chain of the secondary ligand and also with the nature of the solvent medium. The equilibrium constant, K_I of the above equilibrium may be expressed in terms of $\Delta \Delta \log K$ by the expression¹²,

$$K_I = 10^{\Delta \Delta \log K} - 1 \quad (3)$$

and the percentage of the extra-stabilised or interacted form, (%) MAL_{int} may be written as

$$(\%) \text{ } MAL_{int} = [K_I / (1 + K_I)] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

The values of $\Delta \Delta \log K$, K_I and (%) MAL_{int} are reported in Table 2. These values indicate that the extent of extra-stabilisation depends on the stereochemistry of the metal ion and the geometry of the complex, and more important on the size of the noncoordinating side chain of the amino acid as may be seen from the sequence, trp > β -phe. The mechanistic aspects of this extra-stabilisation are discussed later.

Energetics of complex formation and extra-stabilisation may be studied by calculating the free energy changes ΔG_1 ($-2.303RT \log K_{MAL}^M$) and ΔG_2 ($-2.303RT \Delta \Delta \log K$). A quantity, (%) stabilisation may be defined in terms of these free energy changes as

$$(\%) \text{ stabilisation} = (\Delta G_2 / \Delta G_1) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

The calculated values of ΔG_1 , ΔG_2 and (%) stabilisation are presented in Table 3. The free energy change associated with extra-stabilisation is found to vary in the range 0.04–1.58 kcal mol⁻¹. Liquid water exists as tetrahedral hydrogen bonded structure, the energy of H-bonds corresponding to about 6 kcal mol⁻¹. The energy corresponding to extra-stabilisation may, at best, distort the tetrahedral geometry but will be unable to break it.

TABLE 2— $\Delta \Delta \log K$ VALUES, EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT, K_I AND (%) EXTRA-STABILISED FORM, (%) MAL_{int} IN TERNARY SYSTEMS

System	Property	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
M. dipy. (β -phe/ α -ala)	$\Delta \Delta \log K$	+0.06	+0.24	+0.90	+0.03	+0.11
	K_I	0.15	0.74	6.94	0.07	0.29
	(%) MAL_{int}	13.04	42.52	87.40	6.54	22.48
M. dipy. (trp/ α -ala)	$\Delta \Delta \log K$	+0.85	+0.85	+1.16	+0.76	+0.60
	K_I	6.07	6.07	13.45	4.75	2.98
	(%) MAL_{int}	85.85	85.85	93.07	82.60	74.87

TABLE 3—ENERGETICS OF COMPLEXATION : ΔG_1 , ΔG_2 (kcal mol⁻¹) AND (%) STABILISATION OF TERNARY COMPLEXES

System	Property	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
M. dipy. (β -phe/ α -ala)	$-\Delta G_1$	4.95	6.28	10.67	5.74	5.60
	$-\Delta G_2$	0.08	0.33	1.23	0.04	0.15
M. dipy. β -phe	(%) Stabilisation	1.62	5.25	11.52	0.70	2.68
M. dipy. (trp/ α -ala)	$-\Delta G_1$	6.31	8.03	12.03	7.03	6.43
	$-\Delta G_2$	1.16	1.16	1.58	1.03	0.82
M. dipy. trp	(%) Stabilisation	18.38	14.44	13.13	14.65	12.75

This distortion may lead to the formation of suitable polyhedral cages or cavities which may accommodate the hydrophobic noncoordinating side groups of the secondary ligands.

Mechanism of extra-stabilisation: Extra-stabilisation of ternary complexes containing dipy, phen or their derivatives as primary ligand and adenosine-5'-triphosphate¹⁴, phenyl alkane carboxylate¹⁵ or amino acid with noncoordinating aromatic side chain¹¹, as secondary ligand has been found to be solvent-dependent and hydrophobic in nature. The two amino acids under study (β -phe and trp) behave as amphiphiles with hydrophilic aminocarboxylate end orienting towards water and hydrophobic phenyl or indole moiety remaining away from water in the aqueous solution. As shown above, the energy corresponding to extra-stabilisation of ternary complexes may distort the tetrahedral H-bonded network of water molecules creating favourable cavities for housing the hydrophobic ends of the amino acids. The folding of the ternary complex species is, thus, a consequence of hydrophobicity of the side chain of the amino acid. As a result of folding, the amino acid occupies a proximal position with the MA species.

The proximity may lead to aromatic ring stacking (inter-ligand interaction) if the noncoordinating side group of L is large enough to form a stack with the coordinated A. It has been claimed that such intramolecular stacks are actually formed with¹⁶ or without¹⁷ charge-transfer interactions. Extra-stabilisation of some ternary complexes (Pd^{II}, dipeptide, amine) has recently been reported¹⁸ on the basis of noncovalent ligand-metal and ligand-ligand interactions. But the idea of such a L-M interaction in the (Cu^{II}/Zn^{II}, dipy phenyl alkane carboxylate) complexes has been dispelled with¹⁸. Enhanced stability of the ternary complexes (Cu^{II}, ethylenediamine, amino acid) has been attributed¹⁹ to a shift of electrons from the metal ion to the free aromatic ring of the amino acid situated in the axial direction; but this suggestion has been pointed out²⁰ to be contrary to the experimental findings where a more positive $\Delta \log K$ value is observed with a σ and π bonding ligand like α, α' -dipyridyl than with only a σ bonding primary ligand like ethylene diamine. Bhattacharya attempted to explain the extra-stabilisation of ternary (M^{II}, dipy/phen amino acid) type complexes, where the noncoordinating aromatic side chain may reach only the axial region of the metal ion, by arguing that stack formation may not be possible here for the want of sufficient length of the side chain of the amino acid. The enhanced stability may be a consequence of increase in hydrophobicity of the metal ion environment on coordination with an aromatic base like α, α' -dipyridyl, as a result of which the secondary ligand may come closer to the MA species.

It has also been reported by X-ray studies in solid state²¹ that for intramolecular hydrophobic interaction the aromatic moieties need not overlap, orientations other than coplanar may also be fruitful. It may, however, be emphasised that the hydrophobic nature of the interaction appears to be definite and there should exist an equilibrium in solution between the 'interacted' and 'uninteracted' molecules of the ternary complex. Also, since the extent of extra-stabilisation varies with the size of noncoordinating aromatic (or even aliphatic⁹, side group, it is evident that the secondary ligand plays an active role in this interaction. It appears probable that there is greater conformational freedom in such ternary systems (in aqueous medium). In the case of sufficiently long side chains there may even be some straightening of the network facilitating interaction. Work in this regard is in progress.

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